

USE OF DIDACTIC GAMES ON NATIVE LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract. *The article talks about the use of didactic games and its methodology in the process of teaching mother tongue.*

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The essence of modern pedagogical technologies is to give knowledge to the student, to fully master it. The main requirement for teaching in educational institutions based on pedagogical technologies is to provide new knowledge based on the student's life experience, previously acquired knowledge and interests.

The effectiveness of using pedagogical technologies in the educational process is shown by its versatility. It depends on the solution of the questions: "How is the student's mental state, his future development (or decline) taken into account?" In this regard, pedagogical technology has the ability to design, diagnose and differentiate the stages of personality development. It depends on the pedagogue's ability to use educational technologies.

The use of modern pedagogic and information technologies in the continuing education system increases the effectiveness of the student's acceptance and assimilation of educational materials.

Today, different methods are used for the improvement and development of each field, as well as different methods are used in the field of education. We all know that the following methods are recognized as the most basic of modern methods: technology of cooperative education, technology of modular education, technology of problem-based education, technology of didactic games and test lessons. These are innovative methods. By using didactic games in the educational process, active action and interest are aroused in students. The educational process, its development and effective progress largely depend on the open communication between the teacher and the students based on mutual trust. Games in the course of the lesson play a key role in strengthening this environment. Games get used to working in groups and don't take much time. During team work, students become more active and pay more attention to the lesson. Giving students new knowledge, building skills, and stimulating the creative abilities of small group members through games.

The unique aspect of the didactic game educational technology, unlike traditional education, requires the cooperation of the educational activities without banning the independence of the students and the activities of the academic subject, but directing them to the specified goal. Consciously directing them to their activities is considered to increase students' interest in learning the basics of science through effective organization, not to implement any activity by command, and to give them the right to freely choose without limiting the possibilities of individual needs and interests.

In conducting such classes, the teacher must first of all work creatively in order for the student to be moral, to develop the talent of choosing a profession, and to acquire the good qualities of our people. The teacher should be alert and intelligent towards the student, taking into account his interest and abilities, and should treat him like a coach.

Only after that, the didactic game technologies used in the lessons activate the students' cognitive activity, independent work on textbooks and additional literature, development of the culture of speech and communication, consciously guide them to the profession, get the goal right in eliminating the difficulties that arise during the didactic game, analyze various situations, prepares the ground for the correct conclusion. It is known from the manuals that it is appropriate to conduct games mainly in the introductory or final part of the lesson. Games can be divided into types according to their purpose:

"Find words from words" game. In this game you are required to make several words from one word. This type of game encourages students to think, search, and develops their resourcefulness. We will think about the ways to play this game depending on a certain topic, avoiding repeating it exactly.

Several words can be formed using different combinations of letters in a given word. Therefore, it is possible to conduct this game in connection with a certain topic. The game "Word to Word" can be used to teach all levels of the language. In particular, this game can be used in the lexicology department to study the topics of similar and opposite meaning words. For this, the teacher should be able to choose words that can create similar or opposite meanings, and only then bring them to the attention of the students.

In order to strengthen the knowledge specific to the syntax section, it is possible to make simple compound sentences and simple extended sentences from the game. This also requires ingenuity and resourcefulness from the student. Nadir took it. She became a mother. Mother went to Rome. The children looked for Lola, etc. In general. "Word to word" is one of the fun games that you can use. Only in this section it is conducted in the style of "Word to sentence".

In the 5th grade, this game can be used when studying the topics "Simple compound sentence", "Simple compound sentence". For this, our learned students are given the word of natural science and are asked to generate simple sentences from it. The extent to which students can use this game depends on the skill of the teacher and the mindset of the student.

The game "Find words from words" teaches students to be sensitive, intelligent and resourceful. To participate in the game, the student must have mastered the topic well, otherwise, he will be out of the game. If the student feels this, his interest in science will increase. This game can be used to learn all levels of the language. The use of this game is effective in studying the topics of semantic groups of verbs, verb ratios, basic and artificial verbs, semantic groups of adjectives, semantic groups of pronouns in the morphology department.

Application of modern lesson types and forms based on advanced pedagogical technologies, providing a new attitude to the student's place in the educational process means skillful and perceptive management of this process.

Brain Ring game. This game is among the games that form intellectual activity, and 2 to 5 teams of 5-6 students can participate in it. The teacher gives short answer questions to each group. If one of the participants answers correctly first, all the remaining questions will be asked only to this participant, and points will be accumulated for each correct answer. If he does not transfer the collected points to his team's account on time and does not stop the game, but gives an incorrect

answer during the game, all the points that the participant is collecting will be burned. Therefore, that student should stop the game whenever he wants and reduce the points he has collected to the team's account. The remaining questions must be answered by other participants and they will also have the opportunity to collect points at the expense of their teams. 1 point for each correct answer. Below are short-answer questions based on the 5th grade mother tongue textbook:

1. What are the types of sentences according to the purpose of expression?
2. What do we say as a verb?
3. What kind of punctuation is used at the end of a sentence?
4. What do we call an interrogative sentence?
5. What are interrogative sentences used for?
6. What about your father? Didn't he come too? What are interrogative sentences made of?
7. In which bag did you put my book? What are interrogative sentences made of?
8. How do interrogative sentences expressed using interrogative pronouns differ from interrogative sentences expressed using interrogative predicates?

Each game used in the educational process should be explained by the teacher before the students get an idea of the game.

In general, the subject of the mother tongue teaches the student to think independently, to fully express his thoughts orally and in writing. The student's level of literacy, his place in social life is built on the basis of knowledge and skills acquired from his mother tongue. It is known that each national language not only adequately reflects the material world, but also fully expresses the spiritual world, its sorrows and joys. A person has the opportunity to express his attitude towards everything, and this opportunity is always brought to light through certain forms of language.

In short, any modern pedagogical technologies today, by their nature, increase the learning and learning activity of students, allow them to work in small groups and teams, boldly and freely express their personal views on the studied topic and problems, defend their opinions, justify them with evidence, the ability to listen to peers, to further enrich ideas, and to encourage them to choose the most optimal solution among the existing opinions, is of particular importance.

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Today's modern methods are considered as a new promising direction in today's education system. The pupil-student encourages young people to think creatively, acquires knowledge about a topic and is of great importance in forming concepts.

Today we have the only right way to learn the mother tongue. We are required to learn the Uzbek language, which is considered an invaluable asset of our nation, an incomparable jewel of our people's thinking, and to have high oral and written literacy. In order to implement the above, the effective methods can give us the expected results. After all, the era requires both the teacher and the student to search and learn new things.

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